

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF PRICE LIMIT HITS OF TOKYO STOCK EXCHANGE

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Abstract

The primary aim of this paper is to examine characteristics of stocks that hit the limits listed in the Tokyo Stock Exchange. We analyse the characteristics of stocks that hit the limits more frequently, the characteristics of stocks that hit the upper limits and the characteristics of stocks that hit the lower limits. The results show that stocks that hit the upper limits tend to have smaller systematic risk and a stock that hit the lower limit tend to have high systematic risk. This indicates that lower limit hits are mostly due to market driven downward movements while upper limit hits are more likely related to company driven upward movements. This means that price limits rules were effective in Japan in curbing undesired fluctuations of stock prices and in protecting the market from crashes.

JEL classification: G11: G11: G12: G15

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Price limit rules were introduced in order to prevent extreme movement in prices caused by overreaction or noise trading^a. They were introduced to prevent stock price collapse similar to what occurred in October 1987. Following the 1987 crash, most stock exchanges reviewed their trading rules and introduced new microstructural controls such as price limits and trading halts in order to avoid future collapses, stabilise the market and prevent extreme movements. After introducing these new controls, there was a debate between policy makers and researchers regarding the effectiveness of price limits. Advocates of price limits claim that price limits prevent extreme price movements in two ways. First, price limits literally set a ceiling and a floor in the range in which the price can move within a trading day. Second, price limits provide a cooling-off period^b. Other proponents claim that price limits facilitate price discovery by providing a ‘time-out’ to pause, evaluate, inhibit stock prices and publicize order imbalances to attract value traders and to cushion violent movements in the market. Price limits are also said to reduce the potential default risk^c, and counter overreaction, without interfering with trading activity (Cho et al, 2003).

^a Price limits are artificial boundaries that restrict daily price changes of a stock to a pre-specified range. Price limits rules are applied in many stock markets around the world, including Austria, Belgium, France, Italy, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Mexico, Netherlands, Spain, Switzerland, Taiwan, and Thailand. Price limits are also used in the U.S. futures market.

^b See Anderson, 1984; Arak and Cook, 1997; Greenwald and Stein, 1991; Ma, Roa and Sears, 1989a, 1989b; Chou et al., 2000; Lee and Kim, 1995; Kim and Rhee, 1997; Lee and Chung, 1996; Bernstein, 1987; Brennan, 1986; Koders, 1993.

^c See Brennan, 1986; Moser, 1990; Ma et al, 1989b.

On the other hand, critics of price limits insist that price limits reduce market liquidity by artificially interfering with trading activity. This problem caused by price limits is also identified as ‘the trading interference hypothesis’^d. In addition to the liquidity problem, the delay in price discovery is another costly problem induced by price limits. This happens because price limits prevent prices from reaching their equilibrium level effectively^e. The effects of trading interference using price limits may also weaken market efficiency^f. Instead of reducing volatility, price limits may cause volatility to spread over longer periods of time, because limits prevent large one-day changes, and prevent immediate correction in order imbalance ^g. Kim and Sweeney (2000) also argue that price limits can affect trading behaviour on non-limit hit days. In their model, informed traders strategically time their trading taking the existence of price limits into account.

The debate regarding the usefulness of price limits has motivated some researches^h. Among the studies of price limits, some test hypotheses regarding the effect of price limits, for example the ‘information hypothesis’ and the ‘overreaction hypothesis’. The information hypothesis (or the delayed price discovery hypothesis) argues that price limits prevent stocks from reaching their fundamental values. This hypothesis suggests that prices will

^d See Fama, 1989; Telser, 1989; Lehmann, 1989; Lauterbach and Ben-Zion, 1993; and Kim and Rhee, 1997.

^e See Fama, 1989; Lehmann, 1989; Lee et al., 1994; Figlewski, 1984; Kim and Rhee, 1997; Meltzner, 1989; Miller et al., 1987; Telser, 1981; Lee and Kim, 1995; Ma et al., 1989a, 1989b; Chiang et al, 1997; Kim and Rhee, 1997.

^f See Fama, 1989; Lehmann, 1989; Lee et al, 1994.

^g See Kim and Rhee, 1997; Lehmann, 1989; Fama, 1989; Kyle, 1988; Kuhn et al., 1991; Lee and Kim, 1995.

^h e.g. Kuhn et al, 1991; Fama, 1989; and Chen, 1993.

continue to move to their fundamental values when trading resumes after limit hitsⁱ. The ‘overreaction hypothesis’ suggests that noise trading or overreaction drives limit-hit events. After trading resumes, prices will move back to their fundamental values. While the ‘information hypothesis’ predicts continuations in prices after limit hits, the ‘overreaction hypothesis’ predicts reversals in prices^j. Studies of the ‘information hypothesis’ and the ‘overreaction hypothesis’ typically apply event-study methodology to test whether there are continuations or reversals in prices after limit hits.

The analysis of the characteristics of stocks that hit limits relatively frequently as in Kim and Limpaphayom, (2000) can be seen as an extension of studies that test the ‘information hypothesis’ and the ‘overreaction hypothesis’ regarding the effect of price limits. Analysing characteristics of stocks that frequently hit the limits will help to highlight what drives limit-hit events: whether it is information or noise. If firms that hit the price limits have specific characteristics, then we may conclude that limit hits cannot be entirely driven by noise trading or overreaction. Analysing the characteristics of stocks that hit the limit is another way of looking at the effectiveness of price limits rules in curbing undesired fluctuations on stock prices. If limit hits are not due to noise trading then the proposition of price limit rules will just delay the information release process. Hence, the first objective of this study is to investigate whether limit hit occurrences have systematical patterns that are associated with firm characteristics. Examples of these patterns are liquidity, systematic

ⁱ Examples of studies that examined the ‘information hypothesis’ are Huang (2001), Chen (1998), and Kim and Rhee (1997).

^j Examples of studies that test the overreaction hypotheses are Huang (1998, 2001), Chen (1993), and Lee and Kim (1995).

risk, book to market ratio, size (measured by market capitalisation), earning to price ratio, volatility, and residual risk. Characteristics of stocks that hit the upper limits, and characteristics of stocks that hit the lower limits are analysed separately in this study

One contribution of this study is to examine the effectiveness of price limit rules on the Tokyo Stock Exchange, which apply wide price limits rules. However, most of price-limit hit studies in stock markets are carried out on markets that apply tight price limits rules such as the Taiwan Stock Exchange, the Stock Exchange of Thailand and Korea Stock Exchange^k. A market that applies tighter price limit rules experience many limit hit occurrences and this makes the analysis simpler because the analysis can be made using a smaller number of stocks and reasonable sample periods. However, a market that applies wider price limits rules such as the Tokyo Stock Exchange experience few limit hit occurrences. To analyse the effect of price limits in the Tokyo Stock Exchange, larger samples and longer period are required in order to have sufficient limit hit occurrences for the analysis. Unlike this study that covers a long period that includes both usual and unusual periods, previous studies applied in the Tokyo Stock Exchange were conducted on periods of crises (around the year 1990). This makes it difficult to generalize their finding to normal periods. Another reason of the scarcity of price limits studies in the Tokyo Stock Exchange could be that trading rules in the Tokyo Stock Exchange are more complicated than in other markets and were subjected to many revisions. The effect of price limits might differ between markets that apply wider limit rules and markets that apply tighter limit rules. The Tokyo Stock Exchange is a market with wide price limit rules, which is in the range of 20% to 30% of the base price. Taiwan Stock Exchange is an example of a market

^k See, Kim and Limpaphayom, 2000; Choi and Lee, 2002; and Lee and Kim, 1995.

with tight price limit rules. Unlike the Tokyo Stock Exchange that applies different price limit rules in the form of absolute values for different price levels, Taiwan Stock Exchange applies one price limit rule for all price levels in a form of percentage of price changes¹.

The rest of our paper is organized along the following lines. Section one describes the institutional background of the Tokyo Stock Exchange. Section two discusses the data and methodology. Section three contains an analysis of the characteristics of stocks that hit price limits, characteristics of stocks that hit lower limits and characteristics of stocks that hit upper limits. And finally, section four concludes.

1 Institutional Background of the Tokyo stock Exchange

Tokyo Stock Exchange is a typical order-driven market without specialist or market makers to guide price formation. To prevent wild volatility, the Tokyo Stock Exchange sets several market mechanisms such as trading halts, daily price limits, special quote, and tick size rules.

Tokyo Stock Exchange uses trading halts rule in order to reduce the effect of publication of material information on prices. Tokyo Stock Exchange has two types of trading halts; *temporary trading halt* and *built-in trading halt*. *Temporary trading halt* is used when there

¹During the period 1975 to 1998 there were seven different price limit rules applied in the Taiwan Stock Exchange. Between the years 1975 to 1978 price limit rules applied in Taiwan Stock Exchange were plus or minus 5% of the base price. In the period 1978 to 1979 price limit rules were decreased to 2.5%. Between the period 1979 to 1987 price limit rules increased to 5%. The period 1987 to 1988 witnessed a decrease in price limit rules to 3%. Price limit rules increased to 5% during the period 1988-1989. Price limit rules had a further increase to 7% during the period 1989-1996, and finally, price limit rules decreased to 3.5% in the year 1998 (for more details, please see Kim, 2001)

is information that affects investment decisions and the details of such information are unclear. Example of such information is merger, allotment to a third party or a capital reduction. *Built-in trading halt* are carried out when shareholders have to submit their stock certificates to listed companies due to a merger of shares, stock-split, and other capital actions decisions. On Wednesday, December 1999, the Tokyo Stock Exchange amended its temporary trading halt. Temporary trading halt were reduced from 90 to 60 minutes possibly to the belief that information can be released and observed quicker than was previously possible due to technology and advertisements^m.

Tick size is the increment by which prices move. It is vital when placing limit orders, as it determines the possible prices available. In the Tokyo Stock Exchange there is a positive relationship between minimum price fluctuations (tic size) and price level. Tick size rules were subject to two revisions, the first revision took place in April 13 1998, and the second revision took place on July 17, 2000. Table 1.1 presents the new and old tick size rules.

*** insert table 1.1 ****

Tokyo Stock Exchange imposes daily price limits. According to the Tokyo Stock Exchange Fact Book (2003) price limit rules have two major purposes; initially they protect investors from excess volatility. Price limits rules also play an important role in guiding price formation in the Tokyo Stock Exchange, which is a pure order-driven market that has no specialists or market makers. The base price of daily price limits is determined according to the previous day's closing price except in the cases of special quote or ex-dividend date. Special quotes are applied when there is a marked imbalance between buy and sell orders.

^m See Guide to TSE Trading Methodology, 2003, Tokyo Stock Exchange.

If this situation persists at the close of trading, the special quote is used as a base price instead of the closing prices. Ex-dividend date is three business days before the shareholder confirmation date. Since most stock prices in the Tokyo Stock Exchange include cash dividends, an amount equivalent to the cash dividend must be deducted after the ex-dividend date.ⁿ On Monday 17 July 2000, Tokyo Stock Exchange amended its Daily Price limits on the stocks. This adjustment took place because of the replacement of computerised order-routing and executing system for stocks (around mid-2000). Daily price limits are set out in the table 1.2 below. (Maghyereh et al, 2007; Nobanee, 2007; Nobanee and Alhajjar, 2009).

*** insert table 1.2 ***

As mentioned earlier, the base price of daily price limits is determined according to the previous day's closing price except in the cases of special quote or ex-dividend date. Special quotes are mechanisms to prevent short-term wild price movements. For example, if prices make a big jump during the trading session from ¥ 2000 to ¥2200, then market orders placed could be executed at unexpected and unbearable prices and this causes heavy losses for investors who are placing market orders. Immediate execution of orders in the Tokyo Stock Exchange only takes place if the next execution price is set within certain parameters based on the previous execution price^o. Similar to price limit rules, there are different special quote rules for different price levels. Following the replacement of computerised order-routing and executing system for stocks (around mid-2000), Tokyo

ⁿ See Guide to Tokyo Stock Exchange Trading Methodology, 2003.

^o See Guide to Tokyo Stock Exchange Trading Methodology, 2003.

Stock Exchange amended its special quotes. The old and the current special quotes rules are set out in the table 1.3 below. Returning to the previous example of special quote, if the stock price is ¥ 2000, according to the old and current special quote rules this price can only fluctuate to plus or minuses ¥30, the next execution price must be within the range ¥ 1970 to ¥ 2030.

*** insert table 1.3 ***

Tokyo Stock Exchange employs two-trading methods: *Itayose* and *Zaraba*. *Itayose* is a call auction mechanism while *Zaraba* is continuous trading mechanism. Trading starts with *Itayose* where buy and sell order accumulate; an equilibrium price is determined for buy and sell, and then all the orders are executed in these prices according to the price priority principle. This principle means that the lowest sell and highest buy orders take preference. After the *Itayose* clears, *Zaraba*, which is the continuous price-setting method, is used during the continuous trading session to match orders during the rest of the trading session.^P

Short selling is restricted in the Tokyo Stock Exchange. Chung et al. (1994) argues that short selling in the Tokyo Stock Exchange is more difficult and more costly than on the New York Stock Exchange. The major impediment to short selling in Japan is the difficulty or even impossibility of borrowing stocks to sell short. They inference that because of short sale difficulties in Tokyo, good news is likely to be revealed faster in spot prices than bad news (see Chung et al., 1994).

^P See Guide to Tokyo Stock Exchange Trading Methodology, 2003.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1. Data

Daily data is collected for all stocks listed in the Tokyo Stock Exchange during the sample period of this study, 1 January 1990 until 12 July 2002. Several exclusion criteria are applied to the original data. First, preferred stocks and newly issued common stocks are excluded from the sample^q. After exclusions, the sample of this study contains 1467 companies^r. The data set in this study includes daily closing prices, daily volume, daily market capitalisation, daily return index, daily earnings to price ratio, and daily book to market value. The above data are used to measure turnover ratio and stock return volatility. The data were downloaded from the *Datastream* and the Tokyo Stock Exchange website.

Limit hits are determined according to price limits rules shown on Table 1.2. According to price limits rules prices can only move within a specific ranges according to the base price which is usually the previous day closing price except for the cases of ex-dividend days and special quotes^s. Base prices are adjusted for cash dividends. An amount equivalent to the

^q Price limits are relaxed for the newly listed stocks in the first few days after they are listed in the market because they do not have base prices (base price is usually the previous days' closing price except of some cases).

^r Long period and large number of companies is selected due to the fact that the Tokyo Stock Exchange applies wider price limits rules than other markets. This makes limit hit events rare. Choosing a long period also makes the analysis to cover both normal periods and crisis periods (periods of crisis such as the years, 1990, 1997 and 2000).

^sFor example, a stock with a base price of ¥25,000, trading may take place between ¥27,000 and ¥23,000 according to old price limits rules that cover the period 1 January 1990 to 12 July 2000. However, in the period of the current price limit rules, which is applied on 12 July 2000 to 12 July 2002, for a stock with a base price of ¥25,000, trading may take place between ¥28,000 and ¥22,000.

dividend payment is deducted from the closing price of the day previous to the ex-dividend date^t. Base prices are also adjusted for corporate actions such as stock splits and stock dividends^u.

Tick size rules described on table 1.1 were also considered when identifying limit hit occurrences. If closing prices were very close to the maximum or minimum limit hits and the differences between closing prices and maximum or minimum limit hits is less than the tick size, this means that these prices cannot move further and trading is suspended on these stocks. Such cases are considered as a limit hits^v. However, special quotes were not considered in the analysis because data on special quotes is not available on the *Datastream* or Tokyo Stock Exchange website^w.

^t For example, for stock with cash dividend of ¥10, the base price on the ex-dividend date is the previous day's closing price minus ¥10. Therefore, if the previous day's closing price was ¥25,000, the base price on the ex-dividend date will be ¥24,990 and trading may take place between ¥27,990 and ¥22,990 according to current price limit rules.

^u For example if the closing price was ¥25,000 and there was a 1 to 2 stock splits, the base price for the following trading day will be ¥25,000 divided by 2 and this will be equal to ¥12,500 and trading on the following day may take place between ¥14,500 and ¥10,500.

^v For example, if the base price was ¥25,000 and during the day, and just a short period before the market close, the price reaches ¥27,910, this stock cannot reach its maximum price limits which is ¥28,000 (according to current price limit rules applied in the period of 12 July 2000 to 12 July 2002) because according to current tick size rules applied in the same period, this stock can only move by ¥100 and the difference between the maximum limit and the closing price is ¥90. This case is considered as upper limit hit. All the three tick size regimes applied in the Tokyo Stock Exchange are considered in the analysis.

^w After limit hits events are identified, occurrences where prices are greater (lesser) than their allowed price fluctuations were discovered. There are several explanations for this, for example, sometimes trading on a stock is suspended for

2.2. The Models

As the Tokyo Stock Exchange applies wider price limit rules, this makes limit hit occurrences rare compared with other stock exchanges with tighter price-limit rules. A choice of binary logistic regression is more appropriate for the analysis since the dependent variable will be in the form of categorical variable. Based on the median of all limit hits; occurrences of all limit hits are categorised into three groups: stocks that do not hit limits at all, all the stocks above the median of all limit hits are categorised into stocks that hit the limits more frequently, and all the stocks below the median of all limit hits are categorised into stocks that hit the limits less frequently^x. Three binary logistic regression models are applied. The first model tests the characteristics of stocks that hit the limits more frequently, the second model is for the characteristics of stocks that hit the upper limits. The final model is applied for the characteristics of stocks that hit the lower limits. The following equations represent the three models:

$$Y_{1i} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{BTMV} + \beta_2 \text{LGMV} + \beta_3 \text{TOR} + \beta_4 \text{EP} + \beta_5 \text{CONV} + \beta_6 \text{RESID} + \beta_7 \text{BETA} + \varepsilon_i \quad (2.1)$$

$$Y_{2i} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{BTMV} + \beta_2 \text{LGMV} + \beta_3 \text{TOR} + \beta_4 \text{EP} + \beta_5 \text{CONV} + \beta_6 \text{RESID} + \beta_7 \text{BETA} + \varepsilon_i \quad (2.2)$$

several days because of the price limits rules and investors placed orders targeting at prices beyond the limits as a response to some information. In such cases Tokyo Stock Exchange will widen price limits for these stocks. Also if prices were stuck at the limits for a series of three days, price limit rules will be doubled on the fourth day, and limit hit rules will be back to normal in the fifth day. However, in this study situations where prices exceed their limits are treated as limit hit occurrences. This is because they reached their limits by definition.

^x Median of limit hits for the full period (1990-2002) is 4, while median of limit hits for each year of the study is 1 except of the year 1990 where median of limit hits is 2.

$$Y_{3i} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{BTMV} + \beta_2 \text{LGMV} + \beta_3 \text{TOR} + \beta_4 \text{EP} + \beta_5 \text{CONV} + \beta_6 \text{RESD} + \beta_7 \text{BETA} + \varepsilon_i \quad (2.3)$$

Where Y_{1i} in the equation (2.1) represent the dependent variable, which has two categories, the first category takes the value of 0, which represents stocks that do not hit the limits and the second category takes the value of 1, which represents stocks that frequently hit the limits. Y_{2i} in the equation (2.2) represents the dependent variable, which also has two categories: the first category takes the value of 0, which represents stocks that don't hit the limits, while the second category takes the value of 1 which represents stocks that hit the upper limits. And finally Y_{3i} in the equation (2.3) represents the dependent variable, which has two categories: the first category takes the value of 0, which represents stocks that do not hit the limits, while the second category takes the value of 1 which represents stocks that hit the lower limits.

The three logit models applied in this study have similar explanatory variables, which include: book to market value (BTMV), Logarithm of market value (MV), turnover ratio (TOR), earnings to price (EP), conditional variance (CONV), residual risk (RESD), and Beta (BETA) as a measure of systematic risk. α refers to the constant and ε refers to the error term. The book value to market value divides the net book value by the market value. The market value is the share price multiplied by the number of ordinary shares in issue while the book value is the net tangible assets. Unlike previous studies, liquidity is measured in this study by turnover ratio^y. Turnover ratio is measured by dividing trading volume over market capitalisation. Earning to price ratio is the earnings per share divided

^y Trading volume is not used in this study as a measure of liquidity to avoid cases where increasing volume is caused by increases in shares outstanding rather than increases in trading activities.

by stock price. Residual Risk is the standard deviation of the non-standardised residual series obtained from the EGARCH results. Systematic risk reflects the sensitivity of stock return to changes in market return, stocks with high systematic risk tend to have more response to the changes in market return which reflects public information that affects the market. Systematic risk is measured by beta coefficient of the market model proposed by Sharpe (1964),

$$R_i = \alpha_i + \beta_i R_m + \varepsilon_i \quad (2.4)$$

where R_i is stock return, R_m is market return, α_i is the intercept, β_i is the beta coefficient, which represents systematic risk, and ε_i is the error term.

Stock return volatility is measured in this study using EGARCH, which has proposed by Nelson (1991). EGARCH is applied in this study in order to measure stock return volatility for the following reasons. First, it allows for the information asymmetry, the leverage effect g in the model captures the asymmetric effect of the good news and bad news. In Tokyo Stock Exchange good news is more likely to reveal faster in spot prices than bad news due to the restricted short selling (Chung et al, 1994). Second, unlike GARCH specification, the EGARCH model, specified in logarithms, does not impose the non-negativity constraints on parameters. Finally, modelling volatility in logarithms reduce the effect of outliers on the estimation results. The EGARCH model is defined as:

$$\ln(\sigma_t^2) = \alpha_t + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \beta_k g(z_{t-k}), \quad \beta_1 \equiv 1 \quad (2.5)$$

Where α_t and β_k are real numbers, z_t is an iid (0, 1) noise with symmetric distribution, and the function g is suitably chosen to model the asymmetry in the reaction to bad and good news (leverage effect). Nelson suggests using:

$$g(z_t) \equiv \theta z_t + \lambda [|z_t| - E|z_t|]. \quad (2.6)$$

Where θ and λ are fixed parameters such that $\theta^2 + \lambda^2 \neq 0$.

For the iid noise sequence (z_t) , Nelson takes the Generalized Error Distribution GED (ν)

for $\nu > 0$, the density is given by:

$$f(z) = \frac{\nu \exp \left[-(1/2)|z/\lambda|^\nu \right]}{\lambda 2^{(1+1/\nu)} \Gamma(1/\nu)}, \quad -\infty < z < \infty, \quad 0 < \nu \leq \infty, \quad (2.7)$$

Where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function and,

$$\lambda \equiv \left[2^{(-2/\nu)} \Gamma(1/\nu) / \Gamma(3/\nu) \right]^{1/2} \quad (2.8)$$

The choice $\nu = 2$ corresponds to the standard normal distribution. EGARCH model is mainly suggested and used for modelling stock return volatility (e.g. Nelson, 1991).

Logit regression requires fewer assumptions than OLS regression. It assumes no autocorrelation and no multicollinearity between the independent variables. Unlike the OLS regression, logit regression does not require normality of errors and homogeneity of variance.

Binary logit regression is assessed by measuring how well the model accurately classifies cases into the two categories described previously. The overall predictive accuracy is measured by dividing the number of predicted cases by the actual number of cases^Z. Durbin-Watson statistics is used to test the presence of first-order autocorrelation in the residuals. Two Multicollinearity tests are applied, Tolerance and Variable Inflation Factor (VIF). The Tolerance of a variable i is defined as $1 - r^2_j$ where r^2_j is the multiple correlation coefficient when the independent variable is predicted from other independent variables. The larger the Tolerance values the less the multicollinearity. The VIF is $1/\text{Tolerance}$; it is the number of times the variance of the corresponding parameter estimate is increased due to multicollinearity as compared to what it would be if there were no multicollinearity. There is no formal cut-off value to use with VIF for determining the presence of multicollinearity^{aa}. In this study a cut-off value of 5 for the VIF and 0.2 for tolerance is applied. This means an independent variable with a VIF value greater than 5 and tolerance value less than 0.2 is considered having an excess multicollinearity and it is omitted from the model. Each explanatory variable that passed the two diagnostic tests is listed with a B coefficient and tested for significance using the Wald statistics.

^Z For example if the actual number of limit hit events was 1000, and the model predicted 900 limit hit events, then the overall predictive accuracy is 90% which is 900/1000. If the model predicts 400 cases of the first category of the model, e.g. the non-limit hit events and the actual number of this category was 460. Then the predictive accuracy for this category is 87%, which is 400/460. If the model predicted 500 cases of the second category, for example the frequently limit hit events category, and the actual number of this category was 540. Then the predictive accuracy for this category is 93%, which is 500/540.

^{aa} (see, P.D. Allison, Logistic Regression Using the SAS System, SAS Institute, 1999).

Logit regression produces the B coefficient, which represents the effect of one-unit change in the explanatory variable on the dependent variable in the form of log odds ratio or logit. Logit regression also produces Wald statistics, which is used to test the null hypothesis that each B coefficient of the model is zero. The model's χ^2 tests the null hypothesis that all the coefficients in the model (except the constant) are simultaneously zero against the alternative hypothesis that at least one coefficient is non-zero. Two different R^2 are produced with the logit regression output: the Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 and the Cox and Snell R^2 . Hosmer and Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test compares the observed values with the predicted values, and the difference has a χ^2 distribution. In the test of the goodness-of-fit, we hope to find non-significant differences between the observed and the predicted events.

3. Empirical results

Initially, occurrences of all, upper, and lower limit hits are identified. Table 3.1 summarises the occurrences and percentages of all, upper and lower limit hits for the full period (1990-2002) and for each year of the study. Percentages of all limit hits are varying across years. The year 1990 has the highest amount of all limit hits (23%) compared with all limit hits in all other years. The high occurrences of all limit hits in the year 1990 are explained by the crises that occurred in the Japanese market during the year 1990 and the gulf war. Table 3.1 also reports the percentages of upper and lower limit hits. The results show that even in the years of crises, upper limit hits are about two thirds of the occurrences of all limits. For example, 66% of all limit hits occurred in the year 1990 are upper limit hits and only 34% are lower limit hits. Although the price limit rules were raised in the year 2000, the number

of stocks affected by this amendment is very small, and there is no considerable price limit hits in the year 2000 following the revision of price limit rules^{bb}.

*** insert table 3.1 ***

Table 3.2 reports occurrences and percentages of stocks that hit the limits more frequently, stocks that hit the limits less frequently and stocks that don't hit the limits at all. Limit hit occurrences are also grouped into: stocks that do not hit the limits, stocks that hit only upper limit and never hit lower limits in each study sample period, stocks that only hit lower limits and never hit upper limits in each study sample period, and stocks that hit upper and lower limits. In this Paper we analysed the characteristics of stocks that hit the limits more frequently, the characteristics of stocks that hit the lower limits and the characteristics of stocks that hit the upper limits.

The result on table 3.2 shows that the number of stocks that don't hit the limits varies between different periods. It could be up to 1260 or 94.8% as in the year 2002, or it could be 147 or 10% as in the full period. This is also the case of all other sub-samples, for

^{bb}The new price limit rules only affect stocks with high price levels (mainly stocks that are over ¥10 millions) and price limit rules for stocks at other price levels are kept similar to old price limit rules except for minor changes (see table 1.2). It seems that the regulators of the market were optimistic about stock price increases in the future in setting such changes. However, prices continued to decrease afterwards. In my data, which includes 1467 companies accounted for all stocks traded in the Tokyo Stock Exchange, all the closing prices are less than ¥1million except one company. We originally planned to analyse the effect of price limits under the two different price-limit regimes. However, since the changes of the price limits rules mainly affect stocks with high price levels, which are not common as shown on Table 1.2, and affect only a small numbers of stocks (less than 10 stocks) in my sample. This makes analysing the effects of price limits between the two price-limit regimes infeasible in this study.

example, the number of stocks that frequently hit the limits is 14 stocks as in the year 2002 or 1%, or it could be up to 244 stocks or 17% as in the year 1990.^{cc}

*** insert table 3.2 ***

Binary logit results and diagnostics for characteristics of stocks that hit the limits more frequently, stocks that hit upper limits, and stocks that hit lower limits are shown in tables 3.3 to 3.8 below. Multicollinearity results for the first model that tests the characteristics of stocks that hit the limits more frequently are reported in Table 3.3 Variable Inflation Factor (VIF) is greater than 5 for some of the explanatory variables, tolerance values is also less than 0.2 for some of the explanatory variables. The majority of the cases where the results show high multicollinearity are between conditional volatility and residual risk in most of the years. Since conditional volatility is more important to the analysis than residual risk, it is kept in the model and residual risk is excluded from the models in the periods that show high multicollinearity. Multicollinearity results for the second model that tests the characteristics of stocks that hit upper limits and the third model that examines the characteristics of stocks that hit lower limits are reported in Tables 3.5 and 3.7 respectively.

^{cc} The total number of companies analysed on this study is 1467 companies. This number varies across different periods because of the dead companies. For example, the total number of companies analysed in the year 1991 is 1462. This means the number of dead companies in that year is 5. The total number of companies keeps decreasing to 1329 companies in the year 2002. This means that the number of dead companies in that year is 138 companies (1467-1329). Percentages of each sub-sample are computed according to the number of companies analysed in each period. They are not computed according to the total number of companies, which is 1467.

Multicollinearity results of the second and third model are similar to multicollinearity results for the first model. After excluding variables that cause high multicollinearity from the models, VIF and tolerance values back to normal for all explanatory variables.

Durbin-Watson statistics is used to test the presence of first-order autocorrelation in the residuals for the three models. The results for the three models (reported in the Tables: 3.4, 3.6 and 3.8) show that all Durbin-Watson coefficients are close to 2. This means that first-order autocorrelation does not exist in all the models for all the sample periods of the study.

Goodness-of-fit statistics for the three models are also presented in Tables: 3.4, 3.6 and 3.8. Hosmer and Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test compares the observed values with the predicted values, it is distributed as a chi-square value. When comparing observed and predicted events in the contest of testing the goodness-of-fit, we hope to find a non-significant probability. The results of Hosmer and Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test for the three models show that χ^2 statistics are insignificant for all the three models in all sample periods (see Tables 3.4, 3.6 and 3.8). The percentage correctly classified is a measure of the classificatory efficiency of the model and how much the model predicted the observed values. The result shows that the overall predictive accuracy for the first model (characteristics of stocks that frequently hit the limits) is very high for all sample periods of the study, the maximum value is 99.3% in the year 2002, and the minimum value is 88.3% in the year 1999(see Table 3.4). The result also shows that the overall predictive accuracy for the second model (characteristics of stocks that hit the upper limits) is also very high. All the overall predictive accuracy percentages are higher than 80% except in the year 1990 where the overall predictive accuracy percentage is 72.5%, which still a good result (see Table 3.6). Except of the full period, the third model (characteristics of stocks that hit the

lower limits) show better overall predictive accuracy percentage, the figures are around 90% for all the years of the study. The overall predictive accuracy percentage for the full period is 71.2%, which is still high.

The results also contain two measures of R^2 which are: Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 and Cox and Snell R^2 . Unlike the Cox and Snell R^2 the Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 can reach the value of one. Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 is over 30% for most sample periods of the first model (characteristics of stocks that frequently hit the limits) the highest value is 71.1% for the year 1990 and the lowest value is 15.7% in the year 1998 (see table 3.4). The results for the second model (characteristics of stocks that hit the upper limits) show that the highest Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 is 45.6% in the year 1996 and the lowest value is 10.3% in the year 1998 (see table 3.6). Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 results for the third model (characteristics of stocks that hit the lower limits) show that the highest value is 100% in the year 2002 and the lowest value is 8.4% in the year 1999. Generally speaking, Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 in the first model is higher than the values in the second and third models. R^2 results indicate that the three models have a good explanation power.

Model's χ^2 tests the null hypothesis that all the coefficients in the model (except the constant) are simultaneously zero against the alternative hypothesis that at least one coefficient is non-zero. We reject the null hypothesis because models' chi-square is significant in all the sample periods in the three models (see Tables 3.4, 3.6 and 3.8).

Wald statistics are presented in Tables 3.4, 3.6, and 3.8 for the three models. The Wald statistics are used to test the null hypothesis that each coefficient of the model is zero. Wald results for the first model (characteristics of stocks that frequently hit the limits) show that

Wald statistics in the full period are significant for some of the explanatory variables, which are market value (which is also a measure of size), residual risk, and systematic risk. Coefficients for these explanatory variables show that the coefficients for market value and residual risk are positive, while coefficients of systematic risk are negative. These results suggest that stocks that frequently hit the limits in the full period have higher market value (or they are large in size), high residual risk, and low systematic risk. These are the results for the full periods, however results for each year are varying. But generally speaking, as appears in Table 3.4 Wald statistics are significant and coefficients are positive for Market Value, Conditional Volatility, and Residual Risk in most of the sample periods of the study. The results also show that Wald statistics are significant and coefficients are negative for systematic risk in most of the sample periods of the study. These results suggest that higher market capitalisation stocks hit the limits more frequently than stocks with lower market capitalisation; higher volatility stocks hit the limits more frequently than lower volatility stocks; stocks with high residual risk hit the limits more frequently than stocks with low residual risk; and finally, low systematic risk stocks hit the limits more frequently than higher systematic risk stocks.

Wald results for the second model that examines the characteristics of stocks that hit the upper limits show that the number of explanatory variables with significant coefficients is varying across the sample periods of the study. Generally, Wald statistics and coefficients reported in Table 3.6 indicate that higher market capitalisation (or large size) stocks hit upper limits more than stocks with lower market capitalisation (or small size); stocks with low turnover ratio (less liquid stocks) hit upper limits more than stocks with high turnover ratio (high liquid stocks); higher volatility stocks hit upper limit more than lower volatility

stocks; stocks with high residual risk hit upper limits more than stocks with low residual risk; and finally, low systematic risk stocks hit upper limits more than higher systematic risk stocks.

Wald results for the third model that examined the characteristics of stocks that hit the lower limits show that the number of explanatory variables with significant coefficients is also varying across the sample periods of the study. Generally, Wald statistics and coefficients reported in table 3.8 indicate that higher market capitalisation (or large size) stocks hit lower limits more than stocks with lower market capitalisation (or small size); stocks with low turnover ratio (less liquid stocks) hit lower limits more than stocks with high turnover ratio (high liquid stocks); higher volatility stocks hit lower limits more than lower volatility stocks; stocks with high residual risk hit lower limits more than stocks with low residual risk; and finally, high systematic risk stocks hit lower limits more than lower systematic risk stocks. These results indicate that stocks that hit the upper limits tend to have lower systematic risk and a stock that hits the lower limit tend to have high systematic risk. This indicates that lower limit hits are mostly due to market driven downward movements while upper limit hits are more likely related to company driven upward movements. This means that price limit rules did it works in curbing undesired fluctuations of stock prices.

*** insert table 3.3 ***

*** insert table 3.4 ***

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4. Conclusion

Price limits, like many other market trading control mechanisms, are designed to reduce price fluctuations that are due to noise trading. It has the undesirable effect of slowing down price discovery of stock prices if price limit hits are not due to noise trading. The primary aim of this paper is to examine patterns of limit hits for stocks listed in the Tokyo Stock Exchange. We used the patterns of limit hits and explanation theory to inspect if price limit hits in the Tokyo Stock Exchange is due to noise trading.

The results of the analysis suggest that upper limit hits are about two third of total limit hits even in the periods of crisis. This study also discusses the characteristics of stocks that frequently hit the limits, stocks that hit the upper limits, and stocks that hit the lower limits. The discussion of such characteristics will contribute to the understanding of the patterns of limit hits. Analysing the characteristics of stocks that hit the limit is another way of looking at the effectiveness of price limit rules in curbing undesired fluctuations on stock prices. It will also help in investigating whether price limit hits follow systematic patterns that cannot be explained only by noise trading. The results of the three logit models show that upper limit hits, lower limit hits, and upper and lower limit hits vary from year to year through out the sample period. In general high market value stocks, high volatility stocks, high residual risk stocks, and low systematic risk stocks tend to hit the limits more frequently. The results

also show that high market value stocks, high volatility stocks, high residual risk stocks, low liquidity stocks and low systematic risk stocks tend to hit the upper limits. And high market value stocks, high volatility stocks, high residual risk stocks, low liquidity stocks and high systematic risk stocks tend to hit the lower limits.

Specifically, the results indicate that stocks that hit the upper limits tend to have lower systematic risk and stocks that hit the lower limit tend to have high systematic risk. This indicates that lower limit hits are mostly due to market driven downward movements while upper limit hits are more likely to be related to company driven upward movements.

Overall, this an indication that price limits rules were effective in Japan in curbing undesired fluctuations of stock prices and in protecting the market from crashes. Specifically, lower price limit rules were successful in curbing downward market related information and upper limit hits were successful in curbing upward wild fluctuations related to possibly due to speculation triggered by information related to the company.

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Table 1.1 Minimum Price Fluctuations or Tick Size Rules

	Price per share (yen)	Before April 1998	April 1998- July 2000	July 2000- present
Up to	1,000	1	1	1
Up to	2,000	10	1	1
Up to	3,000	10	5	5
Up to	10,000	10	10	10
Up to	30,000	100	10	10
Up to	50,000	100	50	50
Up to	100,000	100	100	100
Up to	1 million	100	1,000	1,000
Up to	20 million	100	10,000	10,000
Up to	30 million	100	10,000	50,000
Up to	30 million	100	10,000	100,000

Table 1.1 Report minimum price fluctuations or tick size rules applied in the Tokyo Stock Exchange. Tick size Rules were subject to two revisions took place in April 1998 and July 2000.

Table 1.2 Daily Price Limits for Different Stock Price Levels before and after July, 2000 Revision

	Previous Day's Closing Price (yen)	Price Limits (before July 2000)	Price Limits (after July 2000)
Less than	100	30	30
Less than	200	50	50
Less than	500	80	80
Less than	1,000	100	100
Less than	1,500	200	200
Less than	2,000	300	300
Less than	3,000	400	400
Less than	5,000	500	500
Less than	10,000	1,000	1,000
Less than	20,000	2,000	2,000
Less than	30,000	2,000	3,000
Less than	50,000	3,000	4,000
Less than	70,000	5,000	5,000
Less than	100,000	5,000	10,000
Less than	150,000	50,000	20,000
Less than	200,000	50,000	30,000
Less than	300,000	80,000	40,000
Less than	500,000	80,000	50,000
Less than	1 million	100,000	100,000
Less than	1.5 million	200,000	200,000
Less than	2 million	300,000	300,000
Less than	3 million	400,000	400,000
Less than	5 million	500,000	500,000
Less than	10 million	1 million	1 million
Less than	15 million	2 million	2 million
Less than	20 million	2 million	3 million
Less than	30 million	2 million	4 million
Less than	50 million	2 million	5 million
Greater than or equal	50 million	2 million	10 million

1.2 reports daily price limits applied in the Tokyo Stock Exchange for different stock price levels before and after July 2000 Revision.

Table 1.3 Special Quotes Rules for Different Stock Price Levels before and after July, 2000 Revision

	Previous Trade's Price (yen)	Old Special Quotes (yen)	Current Special Quotes (yen)
Less than	500	5	±5
Less than	1,000	10	10
Less than	1,500	20	20
Less than	2,000	30	30
Less than	3,000	40	40
Less than	5,000	50	50
Less than	10,000	100	100
Less than	20,000	200	200
Less than	30,000	200	300
Less than	50,000	300	400
Less than	70,000	500	500
Less than	100,000	500	1,000
Less than	150,000	5,000	2,000
Less than	200,000	5,000	3,000
Less than	300,000	5,000	4,000
Less than	500,000	5,000	5,000
Less than	1 million	10,000	10,000
Less than	1.5 million	20,000	20,000
Less than	2 million	30,000	30,000
Less than	3 million	40,000	40,000
Less than	5 million	50,000	50,000
Less than	10 million	100,000	100,000
Less than	15 million	200,000	200,000
Less than	20 million	200,000	300,000
Less than	30 million	200,000	400,000
Less than	50 million	200,000	500,000
Greater than or equal	50 million	200,000	1 million

Table 1.3 reports special quotes rules applied in the Tokyo Stock Exchange for different stock price levels before and after July 2000 Revision.

Table 3.1 Limit Hit Occurrences by Year

Year	Total	Upper	Lower	Total%	Upper%	Lower%
1990	1884	1247	637	23%	66%	34%
1991	802	486	316	10%	61%	39%
1992	874	516	358	11%	59%	41%
1993	407	258	149	5%	63%	37%
1994	278	174	104	3%	63%	37%
1995	440	334	106	5%	76%	24%
1996	425	313	112	5%	74%	26%
1997	503	201	302	6%	40%	60%
1998	419	276	143	5%	66%	34%
1999	787	673	114	10%	86%	14%

2000	836	545	291	10%	65%	35%
2001	292	215	77	4%	74%	26%
2002*	103	75	28	1%	73%	27%
Total	8050	5313	2737	100%	66%	34%

Table 3.1 reports occurrences of limit hits for stocks listed in the Tokyo Stock Exchange during the period 1990-2002. Number of price limit hits is reported by year. Upper and lower indicate the two sub samples of upper limit-hits and lower limit-hits in absolute values and as percentages. Percentages of total limit hits are the number of limit hits in each year as a percentage of total number of limit hits in all years, while the percentages of upper and lower limit hits are the number of upper or lower limit hits in each year relative to the total number of limit hits in that year.

*Data available until 12th July

Table 3.2 Study Samples

Period	Number of companies on each sample						Percentages of companies for each sample						Total
	NLH	FLH	ILH	ULH	LLH	BLH	NLH	FLH	ILH	ULH	LLH	BLH	
1990	666	244	557	447	105	249	45%	17%	38%	30%	7%	17%	1467
1991	1039	184	239	221	114	88	71%	13%	16%	15%	8%	6%	1462
1992	1017	195	246	213	113	115	70%	13%	17%	15%	8%	8%	1458
1993	1190	94	170	160	69	35	82%	6%	12%	11%	5%	2%	1454
1994	1259	65	124	120	48	21	87%	4%	9%	8%	3%	1%	1448
1995	1155	108	180	207	49	32	80%	7%	12%	14%	3%	2%	1443
1996	1222	87	127	147	33	34	85%	6%	9%	10%	2%	2%	1436
1997	1139	107	184	84	144	63	80%	7%	13%	6%	10%	4%	1430
1998	1145	79	194	169	63	41	81%	6%	14%	12%	4%	3%	1418
1999	1018	167	217	312	33	39	73%	12%	15%	22%	2%	3%	1402
2000	1049	167	172	193	56	90	76%	12%	12%	14%	4%	6%	1388
2001	1183	60	114	107	45	22	87%	4%	8%	8%	3%	2%	1357
2002	1260	14	55	47	17	5	95%	1%	4%	4%	1%	0%	1329
90-02	147	795	525	458	82	780	10%	54%	36%	31%	6%	53%	1467

Table 3.2 reports study samples. Occurrences of limit hits are grouped in this table according to the frequency of limit hits, occurrences of limit hits are grouped to: stocks that do not hit limits at all or the non-limit-hit group (NLH), stocks that hit the limits less frequently or infrequently limit-hit group (ILH), and stocks that hit the limits more frequently or frequently-limit-hit group (FLH). Stocks with total number of limit hit (upper plus lower) exceeding the median (of total limit hits) grouped to stocks that hit the limits more frequently, while stocks with total number of limit hits less than the median (of total limit hits) grouped as stocks that hit the limit less frequently. The median of total limit hits for the full period is 4, for the year 1990 is 2, and for the rest of all other years is 1. Occurrences of limit hits are also grouped into four categories: stocks that do not hit the limits (NLH), stocks that only hit the upper limits (ULH), stocks that only hit the lower limits (LLH), and stocks that hit both upper and lower limits (BLH). Occurrences of limit hits reported on absolute values and as percentages for all the sample periods of this study.

Table 3.3 Multicollinearity Results for the First Model (Characteristics of Stocks That Frequently hits the limits)

		All	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002
VIF	BTMV	1.090	1.063	1.122	1.099	1.096	1.124	1.199	1.188	2.362	28.207*	1.355	2.168	1.738	1.431
	MV	1.788	1.570	1.678	1.956	2.177	2.253	2.397	2.123	1.904	2.637	2.528	1.575	1.901	2.082
	TOR	1.862	1.075	1.007	1.305	1.623	1.613	1.354	1.587	5.260*	30.769*	1.227	36.282*	1.652	1.420
	EP	1.111	1.039	1.090	1.053	1.060	1.103	1.044	1.032	1.070	1.417	1.043	1.014	1.030	1.066
	CONV	1.015	1.527	1.011	16.734*	24.973*	14.720*	15.144*	5.449*	11.369*	4.127	10.328*	43.353*	1.270	1.008
	RESD	2.421	2.087	1.518	18.358*	27.597*	17.389*	17.498*	7.253*	4.157	5.194*	12.064*	2.986	2.193	1.938
	BETA	1.281	1.364	1.213	1.526	1.757	1.480	1.502	1.488	1.212	1.215	1.621	1.314	1.411	1.309
Tolerance	BTMV	0.918	0.940	0.891	0.910	0.912	0.889	0.834	0.841	0.423	0.035*	0.738	0.461	0.575	0.699
	MV	0.559	0.637	0.596	0.511	0.459	0.444	0.417	0.471	0.525	0.379	0.396	0.635	0.526	0.480
	TOR	0.537	0.930	0.993	0.766	0.616	0.620	0.738	0.630	0.190*	0.033*	0.815	0.028*	0.605	0.704
	EP	0.900	0.963	0.917	0.950	0.943	0.907	0.958	0.969	0.935	0.706	0.959	0.986	0.971	0.938
	CONV	0.985	0.655	0.989	0.060*	0.040*	0.068*	0.066*	0.184*	0.088*	0.242	0.097*	0.023*	0.788	0.992
	RESD	0.413	0.479	0.659	0.054*	0.036*	0.058*	0.057*	0.138*	0.241	0.193*	0.083*	0.335	0.456	0.516
	BETA	0.781	0.733	0.824	0.655	0.569	0.676	0.666	0.672	0.825	0.823	0.617	0.761	0.709	0.764

Table 3.3 reports multicollinearity results for the first model (characteristics of stocks that frequently hits the limits) for the full period and for each year of the study. Two Multicollinearity tests are applied, tolerance and VIF. The tolerance of a variable i is defined as $1 - r_j^2$ where r_j^2 is the multiple correlation coefficient when the independent variable is predicted from other independent variables. The larger the tolerance values the less the multicollinearity. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is $1/\text{tolerance}$; it is the number of times the variance of the corresponding parameter estimate is increased due to multicollinearity as compared to as it would be if there was no multicollinearity. There is no formal cutoff value to use with VIF for determining presence of multicollinearity (see, P.D. Allison, Logistic Regression Using the SAS System, SAS Institute, 1999). On this study a cutoff value of 5 for the VIF and 0.2 for tolerance is applied. This means independent variable with a VIF value greater than 5 and tolerance value less than 0.2 is considered having an excess multicollinearity and it is omitted from the model.

Table 3.4 Logistic Regression for the Characteristics of Stocks that Hits the Limits More Frequently

	All	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	
B	BTMV	NI	-2.05	-0.81	-0.98	-0.45	1.05	0.71	0.65	-0.72	NI	-0.11	0.07	-0.85	-1.55
	MV	0.92	2.41	1.52	1.82	1.43	1.05	1.29	0.34	0.99	0.67	1.08	1.56	1.92	2.98
	TOR	-0.22	3.65	0.04	1.89	-1.85	-0.16	1.14	-0.99	NI	0.23	-1.14	NI	-0.33	-0.34
	EP	-0.01	-0.06	0.03	0.04	-0.03	0.02	0	-0.19	0	-0.01	-0.05	-0.01	-0.01	-1.25
	CONV	1.63	-0.71	2.09	5.90	6.64	8.83	6.41	8.46	0.25	1.09	2.84	-1.57	-0.46	0.01
	RESD	0.47	0.51	0.3	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	0.12	NI	NI	0.29	0.31	0.37
	BETA	-1.85	2.71	-1.67	-2.00	-1.83	-3.97	-1.44	1.13	-2.86	-1.81	1.01	2.5	1.02	-2.56
	Const	-13.5	-28.93	-15.83	-12.8	-11.08	-10.51	-11.76	-9.61	-8.62	-5.87	-9.85	-18.23	-21.26	-24.32
Wald	BTMV	NI	4.58*	1.24	4.62*	0.44	0.8	1.59	0.47	5.43*	NI	0.21	0.12	4.33*	3.95*
	MV	6.32*	37.29*	21.74*	38.64*	13.66*	2.14	10.95*	0.37	10.21*	5.67*	17.08*	44.87*	21.71*	5.61*
	TOR	0.58	11.04*	0.35	8.32*	1.3	0.01	5.62*	1.89	NI	0.64	11.56*	NI	4.99*	2.15
	EP	0.1	0.28	0.33	1.28	0.47	0.04	0.00	1.33	0.04	0.69	1.07	0.51	0.18	2.8
	CONV	0.18	5.96*	1.35	110.46*	71.44*	38.89*	73.21*	69.57*	0.91	24.64*	75.83*	5.12*	1.47	0.01
	RESD	6.35*	101.78*	10.56*	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	17.81*	NI	NI	26.76*	33.19*	12.31*
	BETA	8.31*	30.42*	29.68*	34.09*	10.44*	18.74*	9.57*	3.40*	37.79*	18.04*	4.62*	47.04*	2.66	1.84
	Const	15.94*	81.98*	43.71*	60.81*	26.99*	7.87*	29.87*	11.53*	19.41*	16.14*	41.71*	86.15*	43.87*	8.29*
Models' χ^2	245.4*	510.0*	364.8*	278.6*	121.6*	110.8*	192.8	244.8*	125.1*	53.5*	167.9*	324.4*	139.8*	44.9*	
Nagelkerke R²	0.522	0.711	0.541	0.437	0.327	0.506	0.406	0.636	0.293	0.157	0.337	0.541	0.513	0.644	
C & S R²	0.310	0.491	0.305	0.246	0.115	0.107	0.181	0.213	0.115	0.052	0.185	0.305	0.143	0.054	
H & L Test χ^2	8.424	9.705	11.868	6.146	8.507	4.375	6.480	4.220	4.288	5.737	9.204	9.360	1.803	0.228	
% Classified	89.7	90.5	91.7	89.8	95.1	98.0	92.9	97.0	94.0	94.8	88.3	91.6	97.0	99.3	
D.W	2.047	1.999	1.917	1.967	1.877	1.907	1.956	2.063	1.965	2.007	2.058	2.013	1.839	1.980	
N1	110	567	898	908	1,080	1,138	1,038	1,098	1,056	1,054	957	983	1,128	1,229	
N2	552	227	171	165	71	37	97	71	84	68	146	152	49	13	

Table 3.4 Reports logistic regression results of characteristics of stocks that frequently hit the limits. The results reported for the full period and for each year of the study. The explanatory variables are: Book to Market Value (BTMV), Market Value (MV), Turnover Ratio (TOR), Earnings to Price (EP), Conditional Variance (CONV), Residual risk (RESD), and Beta. (Const) refers to the Constant. Each explanatory variable listed with a B coefficient and a test of significance based on the Wald statistics. The B coefficient is the effect of one-unit change in an explanatory variable on the dependent variable (which is in the form of log odds ratios or logit). The Wald statistics is used to test the null hypothesis that each coefficient of the model is zero. Models' χ^2 tests the null hypothesis that all the coefficients in the model (except the constant) are simultaneously zero against the alternative hypothesis that at least one coefficient is non-zero. Nagelkerke R² refers to Nagelkerke pseudo R², while C & S R² refers to Cox and Snell R². H & L Test χ^2 refers to Hosmer and Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test. This test compares the observed values with the predicted values it is distributed as a chi-square value. When comparing observed and predicted events in the contest of testing the goodness-of-fit, I hope to find a non-significant probability. The percentage correctly classified is a measure of the classificatory efficiency of the model. Durbin-Watson statistics is used to test the presence of first-order autocorrelation in the residuals. N1 refers to the number of stocks that do not hit the limits while N2 refers to the number of stocks that frequently hit the limits.

Table 3.5 Multicollinearity Results for the Second Model (Characteristics of Stocks That hits the Upper Limits)

		All years	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002
VIF	BTMV	2.250	1.088	1.131	1.101	1.113	1.125	1.185	1.216	1.230	1.309	1.322	2.087	1.619	1.425
	MV	3.402	1.981	2.166	2.402	2.395	2.352	2.314	2.208	2.270	2.669	2.491	1.497	1.952	2.099
	TOR	6.963*	1.227	1.625	1.474	1.576	1.555	1.332	1.495	1.922	1.518	1.283	2.147	2.838	1.391
	EP	1.040	1.056	1.087	1.060	1.062	1.079	1.041	1.024	1.028	1.003	1.005	1.021	1.030	1.061
	CONV	6.456*	4.491	19.373*	19.703*	25.106*	17.051*	9.524*	3.189	22.149*	7.027	1.029	1.079	2.230	1.009
	RESD	3.025	5.314*	21.786*	22.024*	27.995*	19.953*	11.196*	4.633	22.788*	9.617*	1.893	1.926	1.963	1.906
	BETA	1.778	1.625	1.904	1.905	1.786	1.481	1.468	1.472	1.614	1.575	1.463	1.127	1.479	1.309
Tolerance	BTMV	0.444	0.919	0.884	0.908	0.898	0.889	0.844	0.823	0.813	0.764	0.756	0.479	0.618	0.702
	MV	0.294	0.505	0.462	0.416	0.418	0.425	0.432	0.453	0.440	0.375	0.401	0.668	0.512	0.476
	TOR	0.144*	0.815	0.615	0.679	0.634	0.643	0.751	0.669	0.520	0.659	0.779	0.466	0.352	0.719
	EP	0.961	0.947	0.920	0.944	0.942	0.927	0.961	0.976	0.973	0.997	0.995	0.979	0.971	0.943
	CONV	0.155*	0.223	0.052*	0.051*	0.040*	0.059*	0.105*	0.314	0.045*	0.142	0.972	0.927	0.448	0.991
	RESD	0.331	0.188*	0.046*	0.045*	0.036*	0.050*	0.089*	0.216	0.044*	0.104*	0.528	0.519	0.509	0.525
	BETA	0.563	0.615	0.525	0.525	0.560	0.675	0.681	0.679	0.620	0.635	0.684	0.888	0.676	0.764

Table 3.5 reports multicollinearity results for the first model (characteristics of stocks that hits the upper limits) for the full period and for each year of the study. Two Multicollinearity tests are applied, tolerance and VIF. The tolerance of a variable i is defined as $1 - r^2_j$ where r^2_j is the multiple correlation coefficient when the independent variable is predicted from other independent variables. The larger the tolerance values the less the multicollinearity. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is $1/\text{tolerance}$; it is the number of times the variance of the corresponding parameter estimate is increased due to multicollinearity as compared to as it would be if there was no multicollinearity. There is no formal cutoff value to use with VIF for determining presence of multicollinearity (see, P.D. Allison, Logistic Regression Using the SAS System, SAS Institute, 1999). On this study a cutoff value of 5 for the VIF and 0.2 for tolerance is applied. This means independent variable with a VIF value greater than 5 and tolerance value less than 0.2 is considered having an excess multicollinearity and it is omitted from the model.

Table 3.6 Logistic Regression for the Characteristics of Stocks that Hits the Upper Limits

	All	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	
B	BTMV	-2.27	-0.61	0.81	-0.25	0.27	1.01	1.62	-0.01	0.04	-0.26	0.06	0.01	-0.23	
	MV	-0.28	1.03	-0.07	0.92	1.11	0.74	1.20	0.77	0.11	0.61	1.06	1.33	0.99	1.72
	TOR	NI	2.79	3.86	1.75	-0.08	-0.47	1.04	-1.25	-1.98	0.16	-1.26	-1.27	-0.43	-0.49
	EP	0.05	-0.23	0.05	0.04	-0.04	0.03	-0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00	-0.08
	CONV	10.22	3.95	6.91	4.47	5.62	5.94	6.31	0.28	1.66	0.98	0.18	0.02	-0.12	-5.72
	RESD	-0.07	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	0.38	NI	NI	0.18	0.19	0.18	0.63
	BETA	-0.20	1.76	-0.32	-0.57	-0.10	0.39	0.07	0.76	0.14	-0.49	0.66	1.50	1.73	-1.05
	Const	1.14	-9.42	-5.60	-8.48	-10.15	-9.09	-12.03	-14.50	-4.21	-5.63	-11.54	-13.89	-13.08	-22.36
Wald	BTMV	19.58*	0.92	2.01	0.47	0.30	2.73	13.94*	4.46*	0.00	0.05	2.41	0.16	0.00	0.47
	MV	0.51	25.08*	0.06	12.91*	15.04*	5.48*	18.41*	4.95*	0.13	8.51*	24.6*	52.36*	16.05*	10.73*
	TOR	NI	11.99*	20.90*	9.77*	0.01	0.38	6.57*	6.62*	6.87*	0.85	21.59*	23.14*	10.38*	8.87*
	EP	0.58	6.37*	1.10	2.15	1.12	0.36	2.08	0.09	0.26	0.13	0.76	1.74	0.11	0.97
	CONV	4.74*	79.46*	118.25*	80.48*	73.02*	62.25*	108.30*	0.16	30.19*	35.83*	0.16	0.07	0.19	11.18*
	RESD	0.12	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	61.29*	NI	NI	24.85*	91.87*	37.25*	21.26*
	BETA	0.09	35.14*	1.11	4.32*	0.07	0.95	0.05	4.58*	0.12	3.70	2.88	19.22*	15.16*	2.31
	Const	0.12	55.11*	12.54*	35.37*	37.95*	24.15*	55.10*	43.69*	7.00*	23.07*	56.05*	102.48*	59.03*	26.03*
Models' χ^2	130.94*	287.24*	326.04*	158.24*	104.49*	93.77*	250.09*	276.53*	42.76*	57.62*	205.05*	229.37*	147.66*	78.44*	
Nagelkerke R²	0.355	0.352	0.430	0.238	0.197	0.204	0.367	0.456	0.109	0.103	0.307	0.372	0.325	0.391	
C & S R²	0.224	0.262	0.266	0.143	0.095	0.087	0.213	0.225	0.041	0.053	0.201	0.222	0.143	0.090	
H & L Test χ^2	4.975	2.185	8.725	12.896	13.981	5.852	8.692	6.678	11.832	9.644	6.833	12.100	4.664	3.318	
% Classified	81.2	72.5	86.0	84.6	90.5	92.7	87.8	91.5	93.7	88.7	82.2	86.2	93.2	97.3	
D.W	2.000	1.964	1.917	1.971	1.963	1.915	2.043	2.063	1.960	1.975	1.939	1.997	1.974	1.973	
N1	103	566	897	908	1080	1138	1038	1099	1056	1053	957	983	1132	1229	
N2	415	415	213	190	131	102	190	141	74	148	279	183	103	41	

Table 3.6 Reports logistic regression results of characteristics of stocks that hits the upper limits. The results reported for the full period and for each year of the study. The explanatory variables are: Book to Market Value (BTMV), Market Value (MV), Turnover Ratio (TOR), Earnings to Price (EP), Conditional Variance (CONV), Residual risk (RESD), and Beta. (Const) refers to the Constant. Each explanatory variable listed with a B coefficient and a test of significance based on the Wald statistics. The B coefficient is the effect of one-unit change in an explanatory variable on the dependent variable (which is in the form of log odds ratios or logit). The Wald statistics is used to test the null hypothesis that each coefficient of the model is zero. Models' χ^2 tests the null hypothesis that all the coefficients in the model (except the constant) are simultaneously zero against the alternative hypothesis that at least one coefficient is non-zero. Nagelkerke R² refers to Nagelkerke pseudo R², while C & S R² refers to Cox and Snell R². H & L Test χ^2 refers to Hosmer and Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test. This test compares the observed values with the predicted values it is distributed as a chi-square value. When comparing observed and predicted events in the context of testing the goodness-of-fit, I hope to find a non-significant probability. The percentage correctly classified is a measure of the classificatory efficiency of the model. Durbin-Watson statistics is used to test the presence of first-order autocorrelation in the residuals. N1 refers to the number of stocks that do not hit the limits while N2 refers to the number of stocks that hit the upper limits.

Table 3.7 Multicollinearity Results for the Third Model (Characteristics of Stocks That Hits the Lower Limits)

		All years	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002
VIF	BTMV	2.273	1.067	1.083	6.404*	1.101	1.121	1.152	1.183	10.821*	28.908*	1.307	2.284	2.543	1.429
	MV	2.956	1.976	2.164	2.412	2.364	2.271	2.638	2.388	2.056	2.788	2.527	1.563	1.811	2.110
	TOR	5.958*	1.187	1.010	44.474*	462.477*	1.539	1.489	1.401	7.310	31.259*	1.325	39.770*	3.140	1.700
	EP	3.959	1.029	1.055	1.078	1.054	1.098	1.056	1.028	1.095	1.418	1.089	1.017	1.014	1.271
	CONV	1.080	2.995	1.011	87.671*	486.955*	22.022*	6.345*	3.192	7.867*	4.020	11.944*	45.965*	1.495	1.008
	RESD	3.285	3.775	1.855	32.345*	4.053	24.361*	8.261*	4.620	3.906	5.437*	13.239*	2.932	2.350	2.136
	BETA	1.759	1.689	1.300	1.602	1.833	1.467	1.781	1.552	1.284	1.243	1.547	1.105	1.463	1.328
Tolerance	BTMV	0.440	0.937	0.924	0.156*	0.908	0.892	0.868	0.845	0.092*	0.035*	0.765	0.438	0.393	0.700
	MV	0.338	0.506	0.462	0.415	0.423	0.440	0.379	0.419	0.486	0.359	0.396	0.640	0.552	0.474
	TOR	0.168*	0.842	0.990	0.022*	0.002*	0.650	0.671	0.714	0.137	0.032*	0.755	0.025*	0.318	0.588
	EP	0.253	0.972	0.948	0.928	0.949	0.911	0.947	0.973	0.913	0.705	0.918	0.984	0.987	0.787
	CONV	0.926	0.334	0.989	0.011*	0.002*	0.045*	0.158*	0.313	0.127*	0.249	0.084*	0.022*	0.669	0.992
	RESD	0.304	0.265	0.539	0.031*	0.247	0.041*	0.121*	0.216	0.256	0.184*	0.076*	0.341	0.426	0.468
	BETA	0.569	0.592	0.769	0.624	0.546	0.681	0.561	0.644	0.779	0.805	0.646	0.905	0.683	0.753

Table 3.7 reports multicollinearity results for the first model (characteristics of stocks that hits the lower limits) for the full period and for each year of the study. Two Multicollinearity tests are applied, tolerance and VIF. The tolerance of a variable i is defined as $1 - r^2_j$ where r^2_j is the multiple correlation coefficient when the independent variable is predicted from other independent variables. The larger the tolerance values the less the multicollinearity. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is $1/\text{tolerance}$; it is the number of times the variance of the corresponding parameter estimate is increased due to multicollinearity as compared to as it would be if there was no multicollinearity. There is no formal cutoff value to use with VIF for determining presence of multicollinearity (see, P.D. Allison, Logistic Regression Using the SAS System, SAS Institute, 1999). On this study a cutoff value of 5 for the VIF and 0.2 for tolerance is applied. This means independent variable with a VIF value greater than 5 and tolerance value less than 0.2 is considered having an excess multicollinearity and it is omitted from the model.

Table 3.8 Logistic Regression for the Characteristics of Stocks that Hits the Lower Limits

		All	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002
B	BTMV	NI	-0.44	-1.17	-1.03	-2.58	-0.35	0.10	-1.62	NI	NI	-0.40	-0.50	0.33	88.59
	MV	0.22	0.40	0.96	0.66	1.52	0.28	0.17	0.75	0.74	0.09	-0.05	1.41	2.57	255.94
	TOR	NI	1.72	-0.04	NI	NI	0.00	-9.67	-19.17	-0.07	-5.34	-3.53	NI	-1.55	-10.65
	EP	0.01	-0.05	0.05	0.07	0.06	NI	-0.05	-0.05	-0.02	-0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.25	0.61
	CONV	0.12	0.41	0.01	2.71	-31.28	2.32	3.25	5.08	0.37	0.05	0.47	-0.26	-8.67	-512.83
	RESD	0.13	0.13	0.20	NI	1.52	NI	NI	0.06	0.06	NI	NI	0.10	0.82	52.48
	BETA	-2.41	0.11	-1.87	-2.08	-3.26	-1.50	0.11	-3.46	-0.56	-0.84	-1.42	1.48	-0.90	-74.72
	Const	-3.16	-7.65	-9.59	-5.25	-25.20	-4.28	-4.52	-6.48	-7.15	-1.91	-1.73	-13.02	-30.48	-2495
Wald	BTMV	NI	0.22	2.80	5.05*	8.03*	0.49	0.02	0.80	NI	NI	0.74	2.92	0.57	0.01
	MV	0.21	1.34	9.37*	5.33*	10.67*	0.40	0.14	0.56	10.46*	0.12	0.01	20.83*	22.80*	0.05
	TOR	NI	2.04	0.02	NI	NI	0.00	9.56*	5.47*	1.62	7.05*	4.37*	NI	4.51*	0.00
	EP	0.22	0.25	1.88	5.59*	1.67	NI	0.39	0.04	0.40	0.12	0.08	0.16	2.13	0.01
	CONV	0.25	0.36	0.08	27.91*	27.89*	3.72	16.26*	7.02*	1.23	0.05	0.53	4.64*	7.20*	0.06
	RESD	6.28*	6.22*	39.03*	NI	35.23*	NI	NI	0.33	4.59*	NI	NI	6.40*	16.48*	0.05
	BETA	7.22*	0.06	31.76*	35.48*	27.98*	8.01*	0.02	5.53*	3.66	2.52	1.95	7.10*	1.27	0.01
	Const	1.17	10.00*	22.14*	11.67*	38.13*	3.11	3.73	1.25	24.08*	1.80	0.40	28.81*	31.81*	0.05
	Models' χ^2	29.60*	29.95*	86.87*	93.35*	100.03*	13.82*	28.55*	48.17*	52.19*	38.84*	14.70*	63.74*	84.39*	60.84*
	Nagelkerke R2	0.203	0.094	0.187	0.199	0.353	0.054	0.123	0.414	0.097	0.118	0.084	0.275	0.423	1.000
	C & S R2	0.149	0.047	0.088	0.095	0.097	0.012	0.031	0.048	0.047	0.038	0.020	0.077	0.090	0.072
	H & L Test χ^2	3.890	4.385	6.743	5.958	3.453	4.455	8.489	3.119	12.100	5.503	9.026	9.146	1.925	0.000
	% Classified	71.2	89.0	90.7	90.7	96.6	97.2	96.8	98.8	90.3	95.1	97.0	96.5	97.3	100.0
	D.W	2.002	2.012	1.924	1.896	1.933	1.938	1.855	2.110	1.975	2.075	1.997	1.977	2.062	2.002
	N1	117	567	898	908	1080	1138	1037	1098	1056	1057	957	983	1132	1228
	N2	67	82	100	105	46	37	37	15	122	54	28	40	29	11

Table 3.8 Reports logistic regression results of characteristics of stocks that hit the lower limits. The results reported for the full period and for each year of the study. The explanatory variables are: Book to Market Value (BTMV), Market Value (MV), Turnover Ratio (TOR), Earnings to Price (EP), Conditional Variance (CONV), Residual risk (RESD), and Beta. (Const) refers to the Constant. Each explanatory variable listed with a B coefficient and a test of significance based on the Wald statistics. The B coefficient is the effect of one-unit change in an explanatory variable on the dependent variable (which is in the form of log odds ratios or logit). The Wald statistics is used to test the null hypothesis that each coefficient of the model is zero. Models' χ^2 tests the null hypothesis that all the coefficients in the model (except the constant) are simultaneously zero against the alternative hypothesis that at least one coefficient is non-zero. Nagelkerke R2 refers to Nagelkerke pseudo R2, while C & S R2 refers to Cox and Snell R2. H & L Test χ^2 refers to Hosmer and Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test. This test compares the observed values with the predicted values it is distributed as a chi-square value. When comparing observed and predicted events in the contest of testing the goodness-of-fit, I hope to find a non-significant probability. The percentage correctly classified is a measure of the classificatory efficiency of the model. Durbin-Watson statistics is used to test the presence of first-order autocorrelation in the residuals. N1 refers to the number of stocks that do not hit the limits while N2 refers to the number of stocks that hit the lower limits.